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Preliminary Screening and Antimicrobial, Antifungal Activity of *Hormophysa articulate* from the Sea of Kien Giang Province, Vietnam

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Abstract

The study aimed to evaluate the bioactivity of ethanol extract from *Hormophysa articulata* collected in the waters of Kien Giang province, Vietnam. Experimental results determined the presence of flavonoids, phenolics, saponins, and tannins in *Hormophysa articulate* extract. The total of polyphenol and flavonoid content in *Hormophysa articulata* was analyzed to be 26.73 ± 0.06 mg GAE/g extract and 218.72 ± 2.06 mg QE/g extract, respectively. *Hormophysa articulate* extract also showed in vitro antioxidant activity through 4 investigation methods of DPPH, ABTS⁺, reducing power (RP), and TAC. Under H₂O₂ and PQ-induced oxidative stress conditions, fruit flies reared in the medium supplemented with *Hormophysa articulata* extract at a concentration of 1 mg/mL of feed had a longer mean lifespan, 50% survival time, and maximum lifespan than the control which used standard feed. Investigation on the antibacterial activity identified that *Hormophysa articulata* was resistant to four strains of bacteria, including *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Listeria innocua*. The survey result confirmed the highest ability to resist *Enterococcus faecalis*, compared to the other three strains. It can be concluded that *Hormophysa articulata* is capable of synthesizing bioactive compounds with antioxidant and antibacterial effects.

Keywords: antibacterial, antioxidant, fruit fly, *Hormophysa articulata*

I. INTRODUCTION

Metabolic processes inside the cells take place continuously and non-stop to maintain the normal functioning of organism. They contribute to the generation of free oxygen and nitrogen free radicals and cause many dangerous diseases [1]. Many studies on bioactivity are currently conducted to identify natural compounds with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, contributing to preventing diseases caused by oxidation. Seaweed species are known to be used in functional food production due to their benefits to human health. They contain various compounds, including terpenoids, flavonoids, sterols, sulfated polysaccharides, polyphenols, sargaquinoic acid, sargachromenol, pheophytine, vitamins, carotenoids, phlorotannins, meroterpenoids, carotenoids, dietary fiber, proteins, fatty acids and minerals [2]. Brown algae also present analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, neuroprotective, antimicrobial, anti-tumor, anti-diabetic, fibrinolytic, immunomodulatory, anticoagulant, hepatoprotective, and antiviral activities [3]. Therefore, brown algae species are considered a precious source of medicinal herbs at the present and in the future, with their great potential to be used in pharmaceuticals and functional food [4, 5].

The study investigated the chemical composition, antioxidant and antibacterial activities of *Hormophysa articulate* (*H. articulate*) extract, brown algae collected in the waters of Kien Giang province, Vietnam, to demonstrate the potential of *H. articulate* in serving human health.

II. METHODOLOGY

Experimental materials

Samples of *H. articulate* were collected in the waters of Kien Giang province, Vietnam.

The study used wild-fly *Drosophila melanogaster* Canton-S (CS) provided by Professor Kaeko Kamei, Laboratory of Biofunctional Chemistry, Kyoto Institute of Technology in Japan, to investigate the *in vivo* antioxidant.

Investigated bacterial strains included *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC23857 (*B. subtilis*), *Bacillus cereus* ATCC10876 (*B. cereus*), *Listeria innocua* ATCC33090 (*L. innocua*), *Escherichia coli* ATCC25922 (*E. coli*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC27853 (*P. aeruginosa*), *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC25923 (*S. aureus*), *Enterococcus faecalis* (*E. faecalis*).

Equipment and chemicals

Equipment: Autoclave sterilizer (Hirayama, Japan), drying oven (Memmert, Germany), incubator (Memmert, Germany), analytical balance (Mettler Toler, Switzerland), shaker (Stuart, UK), spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA), refrigerator (Sharp, Japan), pH meter (Schott Lab 850, Germany), thermostat (Mettmert, Germany), rotary vacuum evaporator (Heidolph, Germany) and many other devices.

Chemicals used in *in vitro* experiments consisted of 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) (Merck), 2,2'-Azino-bis (3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) (Merck), potassium persulfate ($K_2S_2O_8$) (China), phosphate buffer (China), potassium ferricyanide $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ (China), trichloroacetic acid (CCl_3COOH) (China), $FeCl_3$ (China), sodium phosphate (China), ammonium molybdate (China) and some other chemicals.

Chemicals used in *in vivo* experiments were gallic acid (China), ascorbic acid (China), NaCl, peptone, yeast extract, H_2O_2 (hydrogen peroxide), paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4' -bi-pyridinium dichloride), and some other chemicals.

Extract collection

After drying naturally, the seaweed samples were finely ground and placed in a bag soaked in ethanol (96%) at room temperature. The solution was filtered and collected after 48 hours of soaking. The soaked extract was filtered and collected for 4 consecutive soakings. The extracts obtained were mixed and evaporated to obtain the ethanol extract that could be stored at 4°C for further experiments.

Preliminary screening of chemical constituent

The qualitative screening of natural compounds was carried out based on the method of Jasuja *et al* [6]. The details are described in Table 1.

Table 1. Preliminary assessment of the chemical composition

Compound	Experiment	Identification
Alkaloid	2 mL of ethanol extract was mixed with 3-4 drops of Mayer reagent	Opaque white precipitate
Flavonoid		Orange to red, or blue precipitate

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	1 mL ethanol extract was mixed with 3-4 drops of concentrated H ₂ SO ₄	
Saponin	1 mL of ethanol extract was mixed with 5 mL distilled water and 3-4 drops of ethanol. The solution was shaken vigorously, then allowed to stay still for 15 minutes.	The durable white foam column remains after staying still for 15 minutes.
Tanin	2 mL ethanol extract was mixed with 5 drops of Gelatin 1%.	White cotton precipitate
Phenolic	2 mL ethanol extract was mixed with 2 mL distilled water and 2-3 drops of FeCl ₃ (10%).	Dark-blue or orange-red precipitate

Quantification of total polyphenol and flavonoid content

Determination of total polyphenol content: Polyphenol content was determined according to Singleton *et al* description with some modifications [7]. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent is a mixture of phosphomolybdate and phosphotungstate, used in the colorimetric method of phenol or polyphenol antioxidants. The reaction mixture consisted of 250 µL of extract, 250 µL of water, and 250 µL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was shaken well. The solution was then added 250 µL of Na₂CO₃ 10% and incubated for 30 minutes at 40°C in a thermostat. Measuring the spectral absorbance of the reaction mixture was implemented at 765 nm. The total polyphenol content was determined based on the gallic acid standard curve equation. Results are expressed in milligrams of gallic acid equivalent per gram of extract (mg GAE/g extract).

Determination of total flavonoid content: Total flavonoid content was determined according to the description of Zhishen *et al* with some modifications [8]. The method applied the colorimetric principle to determine the total of flavonoid content based on the reaction of flavonoid with the NaNO₂Al (III)-NaOH chromogenic system. A mixture containing 200 L of extract at a 500 g/mL concentration and 200 L of distilled water was prepared in a tube and shaken well. 40 L of NaNO₂ 5% was then added to the solution and allowed to stand for 5 min, continued to add 40 µL 10% AlCl₃ and kept still for 6 min. After sucking 400 µL of NaOH 1M, 120 µL of distilled water was added to obtain a volume of 1 mL. The spectral absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 510 nm. The total flavonoid content was determined based on the quercetin standard curve equation. Results are expressed in milligrams of quercetin equivalent per gram of extract (mg QE/g extract).

Investigation of *in vitro* antioxidant activity

DPPH method: The antioxidant capacity of the extract was determined as described by Sharma *et al* [9]. Antioxidants will neutralize the DPPH radical, turning the purple color of the reaction solution to light yellow. The lower the absorbance value, the higher the DPPH free radical scavenging capacity. The test was performed on a 96-well plate. 100 µL of DPPH and 100 µL of extracts at different concentrations were in turn added to the wells to reach a total volume of 200 µL. The mixture was incubated in the dark for 60 min at room temperature. The mixture was then measured for absorbance spectroscopy at $\lambda = 517$ nm. The DPPH free radical scavenging efficiency was calculated according to the following formula:

$$E(\%) = (A_{\text{bsc}} - A_{\text{bs}}) / A_{\text{bsc}} \times 100$$

Where E represents Antioxidant efficacy (DPPH free radical neutralization ability) (%);

Absc represents Abs value of the control

Abs represents the Abs value of the sample

ABTS method: The antioxidant capacity of the extract was determined according to the description of Nikolaos *et al* with some correction, based on the principle of reducing ABTS^{•+} ions to ABTS and losing its blue color when adding antioxidants to ABTS^{•+} solution [10]. The experiment was carried out by adding 10 µL of the extract (or standard) to 990 µL of ABTS^{•+} free radicals and incubating for 6 min at room temperature, with the absorbance measured at 734 nm. The ABTS free radical scavenging capacity was calculated as the DPPH method.

TAC method: The antioxidant capacity was determined as described by Prieto *et al* [11]. The method was based on the antioxidant ability to reduce Mo (VI) to Mo (V) and the formation of a green complex. Added 100 µL of the test sample at different concentrations to 1000 µL of solution A consisting of H₂SO₄ 0.6 M, sodium phosphate 28 mM, ammonium molybdate 4 mM. The mixture was taken to incubate at 95°C for 90 min and measured absorbance at 695 nm.

Fe reduction method: The iron reducing capacity of the antioxidant was determined according to the method of Zhu *et al* [12]. The antioxidant will reduce the Fe³⁺ ion in the potassium ferricyanide molecule to Fe²⁺; after adding FeCl₃, a blue complex was formed. 500 µL of extract (or standard) at different concentrations was mixed with 500 µL of phosphate buffer (0.2M, pH= 6.6 – 7.2). 500 µL of K₃Fe(CN)₆ 1% was then added to the mixture before keeping it for 20 min at 50°C. After adding 500 µL of CCl₃COOH 10%, the mixture was taken to centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. 500 µL of the upper layer was collected and transferred into a tube, then added 500 µL of distilled water and 100 µL of FeCl₃ 0.1%. The estimation of the absorbance was performed at 700 nm.

Investigation of *in vivo* antioxidant activity

H₂O₂ method: Male fruit flies which were newly emerged 1-2 days were selected to rear in the medium supplemented with gallic acid (0.05 mg/mL of feed), *H. articulate* extract (1 mg/mL feed), and standard feed. The fruit flies were changed to the new medium every 2 days. On the 30th day, the flies were kept in a fasted state for 3 hours and then placed in a bottle with absorbent paper containing H₂O₂ at 10% concentration or paraquat at a concentration of 20 mM prepared with 9% sucrose solution. The experiment was repeated 5 times for each treatment (each treatment consisted of 20 animals). The number of live flies was recorded after 4 hours of observation.

Investigation of the movement ability

The investigation of movement ability aimed to assess the potential for health improvement that was performed on fruit flies as described by Gargano *et al* with some corrections [13]. Fruit flies that newly emerged 1-2 days were raised in the medium supplemented with gallic acid (0.05 mg/mL of feed), *H. articulate* extract (1 mg/mL of feed), and standard feed. The medium was renewed every 2 days. On the 40th day, the fruit flies were transferred into plastic test tubes (10x2 cm). Each tube consisted of 20 flies. The test tubes were marked with a height of 1–10 cm and tapped simultaneously so that all the fruit flies fell to the bottom. The movement ability of flies was determined by the average height (cm) of the distance that flies were able to move from the bottom up to the marked lines after 4 seconds of tapping.

Investigation for antibacterial activity

The antibacterial method was performed according to Hadacek *et al* with some corrections [14]. The diameter of the inhibitory zone determined the antibacterial effect. 100 µL of inoculum at a concentration of 10⁷ CFU/mL was spread evenly on the surface of a petri dish with a solid LB medium. A well of 6-mm diameter was created with a sterile perforator. Then, 50 µL of the extract at different concentrations was

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added to each well. Samples were incubated at 32°C in 24 h. After 24 h of incubating, the diameter of the inhibition zone appearing around the agar was recorded in millimeters (mm). The test was implemented 3 times, and the average results were taken. The following formula determined the diameter of the zone of inhibition:

$$\text{Diameter of the inhibition zone (mm)} = D - d$$

Where, D means to the diameter of the inhibition zone;

d refers to the diameter of the agar well (6 mm)

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative analysis results of chemical composition

The qualitative results of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, and saponins of the ethanol extract of *H. articulata* are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Qualitative results of some chemical components of *H. articulata* extract

Extract	Alkaloid	Flavonoid	Phenolic	Tannin	Saponin
<i>H. articulata</i>	-	+	+	+	+

(+): present; (-): absent

The results in Table 2 reported that flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, and saponins were present in *H. articulata* extract, whereas alkaloids were absent. The studies of Cho *et al* and Marimuthu *et al* found out that the chemical composition of two brown algae *Sargassum siliquastrum* and *Sargassum wightii* had the presence of phenolic compounds [15, 16]. Nakai *et al* also identified that *Sargassum ringgoldianum* contained phlorotannin compound, a type of tannin [17]. In another study by Akremi *et al.*, the presence of tannin compounds was discovered in the analysis of phytochemical constituents with the biological activity from brown algae *Dictyopteris membranacea* [18]. It can be concluded that the qualitative analysis results of *H. articulata* are consistent with the previous studies on brown algae.

Quantitative analysis results of total polyphenol and flavonoid content

Polyphenol and flavonoid are two compounds with high biological activity, significant in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and hepatoprotective properties. The outstanding advantages of these compounds were that they are non-toxic to the human body and the environment [19].

Table 3. Quantification of total polyphenol and flavonoid content

Extract	Total of polyphenol content (mg GAE/g extract)	Total of flavonoid content (mg QE/g extract)
<i>H. articulata</i>	23.63 ^b ±0.09	150.44 ^a ±3.01

Means ± standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

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The results presented in Table 3 showed that the total of polyphenol content in *H. articulata* was 23.63 ± 0.09 mg GAE/g while the flavonoid content was 150.44 ± 3.01 mg QE/g. The data meant that the flavonoid content in *H. articulata* was higher than that of polyphenol content. Research by Ford *et al* analyzed polyphenol content in brown algae samples by different methods [20]. The results of ^1H NMR analysis showed that the total polyphenol content in *A. nodosum* was 37.35 mg/g of the extract, higher than that of *F. serratus* with 17.00 mg/g extract. Tajrin *et al* investigated the total flavonoid content in the 3 species of brown algae [21]. The results showed that *Padina sp* contained the highest value, which was $0.894 \pm 0.027\%$, compared to the value of $0.786 \pm 0.075\%$ in *Sargassum sp* and $0.745 \pm 0.016\%$ in *Turbinaria sp*. The results showed that brown algae are lower plants capable of producing secondary bioactive compounds such as polyphenols and flavonoids.

***In vitro* antioxidant activity**

DPPH method: In the presence of an antioxidant, the free electrons of DPPH can combine with the hydrogen of the antioxidant to form the yellow DPPH-H. The survey results showed that, in the extract of *H. articulata*, when the extract concentration gradually increased from 500 to 3000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the ability to neutralize DPPH free radicals also increased from $5.86\% \pm 1.20$ to $40.29\% \pm 2.07$. The ability to neutralize 50% of DPPH free radicals has not been achieved. The study of Baihakki *et al* affirmed that, when investigating the antioxidant capacity of brown algae *S. hystrix*, the IC_{50} value was 2861.49 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [22]. Also, the fucoidan extracted from brown algae *Sargassum polycystum* had the ability to neutralize 49.90 - 55.94% DPPH free radicals at concentrations from 200 - 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ [23]. Palanisamy *et al* tested the antioxidant activity of *Sargassum polycystum* using the DPPH method [24]. The three extracts, including aqueous extract, ethanol extract, and chloroform extract of *Sargassum siliquastrum*, showed their antioxidant activity [15]. According to Prasedya, on four brown algae *Sargassum cristaefolium*, *Sargassum aquifolium*, *Sargassum polycystum* and *Sargassum crassifolium*, the scavenging activity of 50% DPPH free radicals was at concentration 737.30, 828.23, 804.30 and 767 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively [25]. The above evidence proved that the antioxidant activity of *H. articulate* extract in the DPPH method was lower than that of previously recorded species.

ABTS method: When the $\text{ABTS}^{+\cdot}$ free radical gains an electron or H^{\cdot} from the antioxidant of the extract, $\text{ABTS}^{+\cdot}$ would be reduced to ABTS, and the blue color of $\text{ABTS}^{+\cdot}$ would be fade.

Table 4. EC_{50} values of the extracts in the ABTS method

Extract	Recurrence equation	EC_{50} value ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Acid gallic	$y = 90.13x + 0.5509$ $R^2 = 0.9852$	$0.5^b \pm 0.0$
<i>H. articulata</i>	$y = 0.2289x + 2.366$ $R^2 = 0.9927$	$208.1^a \pm 3.12$

Means \pm standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

The survey results presented in Table 4 showed that the EC_{50} value of *H. articulata* extract was 208.11 ± 3.12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. In the study of Indu and Seenivasan, in the $\text{ABTS}^{+\cdot}$ method, the extract of macroalgae *Chaetomorpha linum* at a concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ was only capable of neutralizing free radicals $\text{ABTS}^{+\cdot}$ 15.2%, 3.3 times lower than that of *H. articulata* [26]. It could be seen that the extract of *H. articulate* was effective against oxidation in the ABTS method.

Fe reduction method (RP)

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The iron-reducing activity is related to the presence of a reducing agent, a substance with the ability to donate electrons to neutralize the free electrons in the antioxidants. In the experiment, the iron reduction capacity of the extract was determined based on the electron-donating ability to reduce Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} .

Table 5. EC50 value of the extract in Fe reduction method

Extract	Recurrence equation	EC ₅₀ value (µg/mL)
Acid gallic	$y = 0.0537x + 0.0062$ $R^2 = 0.9908$	9.20 ^b ±0.10
<i>H. articulata</i>	$y = 0.0002x - 0.0114$ $R^2 = 0.9954$	2535.20 ^a ±27.30

Means ± standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

The results presented in Table 5 showed that the EC₅₀ value of *H. articulata* extract was 2535.2±27.3 µg/mL, which was much lower than that of gallic acid at 9.2±0.1 µg/mL. The result was reasonable as gallic acid is the commercial standard of high purity, while the extracts are synthetic with many different compounds that may have mutually inhibitory effects.

Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) method

The antioxidant effect of the extract was determined through the absorbance (abs) value of the sample after testing. The larger the abs value, the higher the antioxidant capacity of the extract.

Table 6. EC50 values of the extract in the TAC method

Extract	Phương trình hồi quy	Giá trị EC ₅₀
		EC ₅₀ value (µg/mL)
Acid ascorbic	$y = 0.015x + 0.2352$ $R^2 = 0.9863$	25.13 ^b ±0.46
<i>H. articulata</i>	$y = 0.0031x + 0.1506$ $R^2 = 0.9863$	143.63 ^a ±1.98

Means ± standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

The survey results presented in Table 6 showed that the EC₅₀ value of *H. articulata* extract was 143.63±1.98. Compared with the gallic acid treatment, the antioxidant capacity of *H. articulata* extract was 5.72 times lower than that of the ascorbic acid.

In vivo antioxidant activity

The mean lifespan is defined as the average lifespan of all surveyed individuals. 50% survival time is counted as the time from the start of the experiment until 50% of the survival flies. The maximum lifespan is the average lifespan of 10% remaining flies in the experiment [27].

PQ method

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Table 7. *In vivo* antioxidant effect under 20mM PQ-induced oxidative stress

Treatment	Mean lifespan (hour)	50% survival time (hour)	Maximum lifespan (hour)
Control	12.47 ^c ±1.10	12.67 ^c ±1.15	25.33 ^c ±3.05
Acid gallic	29.97 ^a ±1.29	28.33 ^a ±1.53	56.67 ^a ±4.16
<i>H. articulata</i>	19.50 ^b ±1.57	20.00 ^b ±2.00	37.33 ^b ±1.15

Means ± standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

The results displayed in Table 7 showed that fruit flies reared in the medium supplemented with *H. articulata* extract were resistant to PQ-induced oxidative stress, whereas those reared in the gallic acid-supplemented diet had a mean lifespan of 29.97 hours. The data explained that gallic acid supplementation was the most effective medium at the criterion of mean lifespan. Fruit flies reared with *H. articulata* extract were more resistant than those in the medium without the extract (control treatment), with a mean lifespan of 19.5 hours. In the control treatment, the value only reached 12.47 hours. At the criterion of 50% survivals, the gallic acid treatment was the most effective based on the observed time values. Specifically, fruit flies reared in the medium supplemented with gallic acid had a 50% survival time under PQ-induced stress of 28.33 hours. In the treatment with fruit flies reared in the medium supplemented with *H. articulata* extract, the 50% survival time was 20.00 hours, while in the control treatment, it was only 12.67 hours.

Similarly, the maximum lifespan in the treatment supplemented with gallic acid, *H. articulata* extract, and the control was 56.67 hours, 37.33 hours, and 25.33 hours, respectively. Thus, at the criterion of maximum lifespan, the treatment with gallic acid was still the most effective and 31.34 hours higher than the control treatment. The results also showed that, in the treatment supplemented with *H. articulata* extract, the maximum lifespan was 12 hours higher than that of the control, which means the addition of *H. articulata* extracts enhanced the ability against PQ-induced stress of fruit flies. It can be confirmed that the brown algae *H. articulata* extract effectively prolonged survival time under PQ-induced oxidative stress.

H₂O₂ method

The data in Table 8 presented that fruit flies raised in the medium supplemented with extracts of brown algae are resistant to stress caused by H₂O₂. The higher values demonstrated the tolerance ability through the investigated criteria, including mean lifespan, 50% survival time, and maximum lifespan of the fruit flies reared under the medium supplemented with positive control of gallic acid and *H. articulata* extract than the control.

Table 8. *In vivo* antioxidant effect under H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress 10%

Treatment	Mean lifespan (hour)	50% survival time (hour)	Maximum lifespan (hour)
Control	34.40 ^c ±1.30	39.00 ^b ±1.00	47.67 ^c ±0.58
Acid gallic	48.63 ^a ±0.47	48.67 ^a ±1.16	61.33 ^a ±1.16
<i>H. articulata</i>	38.70 ^b ±0.50	40.67 ^b ±0.58	53.33 ^b ±1.16

Means ± standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

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The medium supplemented with gallic acid showed its effectiveness in increasing the mean lifespan of fruit flies in the condition of H₂O₂ – induced stress by 48.63 hours. Fruit flies reared in the medium supplemented with *H. articulata* extract had a mean lifespan of 38.70 hours, higher than those in the control treatment at 34.4 hours. At the criterion of 50% survival time, the fruit flies in the treatment with *H. articulata* extract reached the value of 40.67 hours, while in the control treatment, the value was only up to 39 hours. Similarly, the maximum lifespan of the fruit flies in the treatment with *H. articulata* extract was 5.66 h higher than the control. Research by Zhang *et al* demonstrated that the fucoidan SP2 present in *Sargassum fusiforme* had antioxidant capacity, prolonging the lifespan of *Drosophila melanogaster* by activating the Nrf2/ARE signaling pathway [28]. It can be concluded that *H. articulata* extracts effectively prolonged the survival time under H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress. The experimental results under *in vivo* conditions reinforced more scientific evidence on the antioxidant activity of brown algae *H. articulata* in Vietnam.

H. articulata extract could improve the movement ability of fruit flies

Using medicinal plants to maintain human health is currently a goal of many scientists. There are many criteria to evaluate the effect of improving and maintaining human health. The study investigated the ability to maintain the health status of fruit flies by examining their movement ability.

Table 9. The motility improvement of 40-day-old fruit flies by using *H. articulata*

Treatment	The distance of movement (cm)
Control	3.65 ^c ±0.17
Acid gallic	5.40 ^a ±0.15
<i>H. articulata</i>	4.20 ^b ±0.18

Means ± standard deviations with different letters in the same row refer to Tukey's test's statistically significant differences at the 5%.

The survey results in Table 9 indicated that the movement distance in the control treatment was 3.65cm. The treatment of flies reared in the medium supplemented with gallic acid had the highest efficiency compared with the other treatments. Flies reared in the medium supplemented with *H. articulata* extract had a longer movement distance than those in the standard medium. The result had a statistically significant difference. Specifically, flies in *H. articulata* treatment reached an average height of 4.20 cm, which was 1.15 times higher than that of the control treatment at 3.65 cm. It was found that flies reared in the medium supplemented with *H. articulata* extract had better motility than those in the medium without extract. The effect resulted in the presence of the compounds with good antioxidant activity in *H. articulata* extract.

Antibacterial results

Bacterial strains causing common diseases in humans such as *B. cereus*, *B. subtilis*, *L. innocua* and *E. faecalis* were used to investigate the antibacterial activity of *H. articulate* extract. The results are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Inhibition zone (mm) of *H. articulata* extract on some bacterial strains

Bacteria strains	Extract concentration (mg/mL)					
	2	4	8	16	32	64
<i>B. subtilis</i>	0.00±0.00	0.33±0.15	0.60±0.17	1.37±0.12	1.87±0.12	2.33±0.29
<i>B. cereus</i>	0.27±0.25	0.70±0.17	1.20±0.17	1.77±0.25	2.43±0.12	2.87±0.12
<i>L. innocua</i>	0.20±0.17	0.43±0.12	0.77±0.25	2.37±0.12	2.87±0.12	3.37±0.12

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<i>E. faecalis</i>	3.50±0.50	4.17±0.29	5.17±0.29	5.60±0.53	6.03±0.25	6.93±0.12
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The survey results showed that the antibacterial effect of *H. articulata* extract increased gradually with the concentration of the extract. At a 2 mg/mL concentration, the *H. articulata* extract has not shown its activity against *B. subtilis*, but presented its activity against *B. cereus*, *L. innocua*, and *E. faecalis*. The highest antibacterial ability was expressed at the concentration of 64 mg/mL. Among the four surveyed bacterial strains, *E. faecalis* was quite sensitive to *H. articulata* extract even though they were known as gram-positive bacteria. In addition, the study also found that *H. articulata* extract did not show its inhibitory activity against three bacterial strains, including *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*. Research by Alam *et al* showed that methanol and hexane solvent extracts of *H. articulata* obtained in Papua New Guinea exhibited activity against the strains of Gram-positive bacteria [29]. Another species of brown algae in the same genus, *H. cuneiformis*, has also been active against human pathogens such as *S. aureus*, *E. faecalis*, *E. coli*, *K. pneumonia* and *P. aeruginosa* [30]. Survey results indicated that *Sargassum wightii* extract contained secondary compounds with antibacterial activity, including flavonoid, phenolic, saponin, and tannin, which were introduced to have antibacterial activity [31].

IV. CONCLUSION

H. articulata contained flavonoids, phenolics, saponins, and tannins. The total of polyphenol and flavonoid content of *H. articulata* extract were determined to be 23.6273±0.0891 mg GAE/g and 150.44±3.01 mg QE/g, respectively. *H. articulata* had *in vitro* and *in vivo* antioxidant activity and showed its activity to improve the movement ability of fruit flies. In addition, the extract of *H. articulata* was resistant to the four strains of pathogenic bacteria, including *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Listeria innocua*. The study results have contributed to proving that *H. articulata* could synthesize the compounds with biological activities such as antioxidant and antimicrobial properties.

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